

Plant Responses to Light Pollution at Different Color Temperatures

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Abstract: With the advancement of lighting technologies and population growth, the demand for plant cultivation in artificial environments has increased. The spectral composition of sunlight typically differs significantly from widely used LED lamps. Plants possess various sensors to perceive light, with certain photoreceptors detecting blue, yellow, and both light and dark red wavelengths, thereby triggering distinct responses at cellular, tissue, and whole-organism levels. However, light can act as a stress factor for plants when it deviates from natural conditions. Our research aimed to investigate how plants respond to nighttime light pollution dominated by either short-wavelength, cool white light or long-wavelength, warm white light. Based on our results, we can infer the specific lighting requirements of these plants. We compared the growth of six herbaceous crop species—*Solanum lycopersicum* (L.), *Capsicum annuum* (L.), *Lactuca sativa* (L.), *Lactuca sativa* var. *aurescens* (Syn.), *Zea mays* L., *Catharanthus roseus* (L. G. Don.), and *Anthemis cotula* L.—under 3000K and 6500K (1.2 PAR) nighttime illumination for 40 days. In addition to growth parameters, we examined photosynthetic characteristics (net photosynthesis, PSII activity, transpiration) and flowering, where flower buds appeared. Control plants grew under natural background light. Significant differences were observed among species in growth, photosynthetic performance, and flowering in response to light pollution from different illumination types. Lettuce and scented mayweed showed the largest growth at 3000K ALAN (Artificial Light at Night), whereas corn, pepper, tomato, and bright eyes grew more vigorously under 6500K lighting. Parameters measuring photosynthetic apparatus function did not correlate with plant size. However, non-photochemical quenching, indicative of stress, was lowest in all species under non-polluted light environments. For the two flowering species, cool white light inhibited flowering and reduced flower numbers. Pepper flowering was delayed or suppressed by both cool and warm white light, with flower buds only present in control plants. The pronounced species-level variability in response suggests that specific lighting environments are necessary for optimal artificial plant cultivation.

Keywords: light pollution; PSII activity; transpiration; ALAN.

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